

Case Studies: Datafication

Case 1: Influence of Social Media on Political Campaigns

Case 2: Retail Services and Loyalty Programs

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CASE 1: Influence of Social Media on Political Campaigns

In a 2014 essay, Professor Zeynep Tufekci wrote, “By holding on to the valuable troves of big data, and by controlling of algorithms which determine visibility, sharing and flow of political information, the Internet’s key sites and social platforms have emerged as inscrutable, but important, power brokers of networked politics.”

Introduction

Big–data driven computational politics engenders many potential consequences for politics in the networked era (Tufekci, 2014b). Since its inception, social media has been in the eye of the storm for using persuasive designs that influence political decisions and voting behaviour. Professor Zeynep Tufekci has expressed strong opinions and has, in various works, underscored the role of digital toolkits in influencing various social movements around the world. Professor Tufekci’s essay speaks densely about how big data is a vote bank and her words are still relevant after eight years. This essay examines two political instances that were digitally fueled and influenced by powerful algorithms executed by social media and other digital toolkits.

Analysis 1

As social media changes the ways news and information is distributed, accessed and engaged with, we are forced to consider its implications for both journalism’s role in shaping public discourse, but also for the way media conveys information back-and-forth between citizens and the political system (Hänksa, Max & Bauchowitz, Stefan., 2017). It is rhetorical to say that news organisations use social media to reach audiences and there is significant evidence which suspects the role of social media in influencing the Brexit Referendum Campaign. Twitter and YouTube are the most popular domains linked with the distribution of information about the campaign and the most popular contents shared on digital media was in

support of Euroscepticism. One possible explanation of the dominance Leavers achieved on Twitter may be that slogans such as ‘vote Leave’, ‘take control’, or even ‘Brexit’ were more suited to simple, soundbite messaging than the Remain campaign’s slogans and arguments (Hänska & Bauchowitz, 2017).

Analysis 2

Since the EU Referendum in June 2016, and even more so since Trump’s election victory in November, pundits have not tired of asserting the supposedly wide-reaching influence of social media on our politics (Hänska & Bauchowitz, 2017). In 2007, Barack Obama was not a well known senator when he was running for the presidential election. But, in November 2008, he won by a margin of nearly 200 electoral votes and 8.5 million popular votes. Many factors contributed to his success, but a major one was the way Obama and his Chicago-based campaign team used social media and technology as an integral part of their campaign strategy, not only to raise money, but also more importantly, to develop a groundswell of empowered volunteers who felt that they could make a difference (Aaker & Chang, 2009). According to Edelman Research analysts, Obama won by engaging and mobilising volunteers, donors and advocates through online platforms such as, social networks, e-mail advocacy, text messaging and online video and that the campaign’s proclivity to online advocacy is a major reason for his victory. In terms of the numbers, externally, Obama’s campaign was able to garner 5 million supporters on 15 different social networks ranging from Facebook to MySpace (Aaker & Chang, 2009).

One might argue that invention of new digital technology has brought new opportunities but many geopolitical observers are of the opinion that social movements around the world have made use of these technologies to express dissent against the existing local or global powers. There are instances where internet connections have been

disconnected to restore law and order in a place. For instance, the Syrian government shut down the Internet in order to control information exchanges among rebels seeking to overthrow the dictatorship of Bashir al-Assad as well as to limit the amount of information the international community could access about events within the country (Summary Analysis, n.d., 2022).

Conclusion

Gandhi is known to be the world's greatest political strategist. Often, he has been alleged to be manipulative and subtly authoritative and has influenced most of the political decisions post Indian independence albeit using non-violent means and merely through influencing public opinion. Today, the role of social media can be compared to Gandhi's political strategies. Computational politics is a set of practices the rise of which depends on, but is not solely defined by, the existence of big data and accompanying analytic tools and is defined by the significant information asymmetry - those holding the data know a lot about individuals while people don't know what the data practitioners know about them (Tufekci, 2014b).

CASE 2: Retail Services and Loyalty Programs

In October 2022, a London Tesco customer took to Twitter to complain that he was forced to sign up for a Tesco club card to shop there:

<https://www.mylondon.news/whats-on/shopping/tesco-shopper-furious-wasnt-allowed-25250840>

The Irish Council for Civil Liberties argued that this is a violation of the right to avoid unnecessary data processing (updated to add that Tesco is experimenting with one particular model of store that makes entry conditional)

<https://www.iccl.ie/news/tesco-barring-store-entry-to-people-who-refuse-club-cards/>

A response from Tesco or similar shops might be that individuals have other shopping options and thus this model isn't a problem, but an opportunity for shoppers to get lower prices/more efficient service.

Introduction

It is a known fact that retail services utilise customer's electronic footprints to optimise their business outcomes. In the given case study, the said retailer giant entices customers into subscribing for a loyalty card in order to avail better deals and the customer is forced to sign-up for its loyalty program in order to be eligible for shopping. The Irish Council for Civil Liberties posits that the scheme entails extensive data collection and processing and the council requests the concerned authorities to take cognizance of this, because entry to grocery stores is an essential requirement of daily life and making entry to Tesco retail stores conditional on that collection and processing infringes the principle of data minimisation. This essay is an effort to support the view of the said customer in the case study and call on the retail services to be more transparent, fair and give consumers a choice.

Analysis 1

Businesses collect and store massive amounts of data, much of which comes from digital footprints and in turn, companies use this information to enhance their marketing, advertising, customer service, and decision-making efforts (Astor, 2017). Many retailers, including Walmart, have particularly targeted loyalty subscriptions to track consumers and market products (CASE STUDY of WALMART, 2013). In the name of providing customised shopping experience, customer privacy is being eroded both online and offline with retail giants tracking targeted customers. This paves way for considerable sensitive information to be automatically used to accurately predict a range of highly sensitive personal attributes including: sexual orientation, ethnicity, religious and political views, personality traits, intelligence, happiness, use of addictive substances, parental separation, age, and gender.” (CASE STUDY of WALMART, 2013)

Analysis 2

Both passive and active data collection has put consumers into the spot and are being used to manipulate them to the retailer’s advantage. For instance, high-end models of Roomba, iRobot’s robotic vacuum, collect data as they clean, identifying the locations of walls and furniture. A customer can opt-out of using Roomba’s invasive feature by not using the app which controls the smart features, but will have reduced functionality and data security. In these Requerimiento-style relationships, instead of the adelantados’ message, “Bend the knee or we destroy you,” the message here is “Bend the knee or we degrade your purchase.” (Zuboff, 2020)

Analysis 3

There is an increase in the prevalence of tracking customers via mobile devices by retail giants for data-driven promotions. Loyalty program data, paints a complete picture of

customer behaviour, preferences and purchase habits which help in targeting them better with relevant information. For example, smartphone-carrying customers are important to Walmart; the company estimates that each month they make four more trips and spend 77% more in stores. Mobile users account for a third of Walmart.com traffic most of the year, and as much as 40% during the holidays (CASE STUDY of WALMART, 2013). Mobile devices offer Walmart and other companies a sort of portal between what might have once been considered our separate online and offline worlds (CASE STUDY of WALMART, 2013). Tesco's promotional strategy has contributed to its sales growth, a 7.5% increase on a two-year basis.

Conclusion

Tesco revealed that 95% of its store promotions are reserved for members of its loyalty scheme, further highlighting the value that it brings (Sebert, 2022). On subscribing to these Loyalty Programs, the customers are extensively subjected to data collection and processing. Retail services might argue that there are other shopping alternatives for the customers, but customers regularly shop from the same retailer for multiple reasons such as, convenience, product availability and customer service. Other factors like value for money, emotional connection, and personalisation can also act as motivation for repeat purchases, ultimately helping retailers build connections with consumers – as well as that all-important set of data insights (Sebert, 2022). With data, retail services can optimise their service and quality of products. Consumers and retailers alike need to be sensitive when it comes to digital footprints (Sebert, 2022). Consumers must be cognizant as to what they subscribe to, while retailers ensure that there's transparency and that the consumers are not forced into sharing personal details unwillingly.

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